

Composite materials for supercapacitor electrodes utilizing polypyrrole nanotubes, reduced graphene oxides and metal–organic framework

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Polypyrrole (PPy) is favoured in energy storage for its high pseudo-capacitive performance, notably as polypyrrole nanotubes (PPyNTs) due to their easy synthesis, cost-effectiveness and electrochemical solid properties. Metal–organic frameworks (MOFs) have also gained attention for enhancing supercapacitors (SCs). In this study, we fabricated aerogel composites with PPyNTs, MOFs and reduced graphene oxide (rGO) as SC electrode materials. Varying concentrations of PPyNTs and rGO were explored, with MOFs added to assess their impact. Electrochemical tests revealed that the composite with PPyNTs and Zn-MOF achieved the highest specific capacitance of approximately 270 F/g at 0.5 A/g.

Keywords: Electrochemical devices, metal–organic framework, polypyrrole nanotubes, reduced graphene oxide, supercapacitor electrodes.

NOWADAYS, technological advancement with regard to various human activities drives a significant and escalating demand for energy consumption. However, the heavy reliance on fossil fuels poses critical challenges such as climate change and air quality deterioration. In response, scientists globally are actively exploring alternative energy solutions, aiming for devices that are easy to manufacture, environmentally-friendly and durable. Electrochemical supercapacitors (SCs) have emerged as promising candidates among these alternatives¹.

The electrodes of SCs can be composed of various materials, such as reduced graphene oxide (rGO)² and conductive polymers³, which have gained attention for their high conductivity, stability and eco-friendliness. Additionally, GO particles can form graphite sheets during the reduction process, increasing the specific surface area and electron mass transfer. However, despite these advantages,

traditional electric double-layer capacitors based on carbon materials have specific capacitance and energy storage limitations^{4–6}.

To overcome these limitations, conductive polymers like polypyrrole (PPy) have been utilized for their pseudo-capacitance properties, with PPy nanotubes (PPyNTs) showing promise due to their large specific area and charge transportability⁷. Moreover, metal–organic frameworks (MOFs) have shown exciting results when integrated into SC devices, enhancing energy storage capacitance through their electrochemical behaviour^{8–10}.

The present study evaluates the effect of one-dimensional PPyNT concentration in composites with rGO and MOFs on the performance of SCs. The composites were synthesized via a one-step hydrothermal method, with rGO as the matrix and PPyNTs and MOFs as reinforcements to improve their electrical properties. The resulting composites were evaluated as electrode materials for symmetrical SCs. Based on previous studies, we have developed composites containing introduced MOF using different Cu²⁺ and Zn²⁺ ions combined with PPyNTs and rGO to improve the working performance of SCs^{2,11,12}. The composites obtained were examined to determine their working performance as electrode materials for symmetrical SCs.

Results and discussion

PPyNT structures were synthesized via oxidative polymerization in a homogeneous aqueous solution containing pyrrole and oxidant of iron(III) chloride hexahydrate. Initially, insoluble pyrrole oligomers aggregated, forming nucleate particles that facilitated heterophase growth of polymer chains, resulting in PPyNT nanotube formation. Methyl orange (MO) was used as a structure-guiding agent due to its stick-like shape and ability to form one-dimensional aggregates in acidic aqueous media. Introducing

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Figure 1. (a) Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy and (b) X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) spectra of polypyrrole nanotubes (PPyNTs), rP20, rP40, rPZn and rPCu.

Table 1. Apparent surface chemical composition as determined by XPS

Sample	Surface chemical composition (at.%)					
	C1s	O1s	N1s	S2p/Cl2p	Cu2p	Zn2p
rP20	85.8	13.2	0.8	0.2/-	-	-
rP40	85.2	13.4	1.1	0.3/-	-	-
rPCu	80.9	15.2	1.6	-/-	2.3	-
rPZn	82.6	14.3	1.7	-/-	-	1.4

MO into the reaction medium induced a morphological change in PPy from spherical to one-dimensional nanotubes⁷.

FTIR and XPS study of PPyNTs and the composites

Figure 1 a shows the Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR) spectra of PPyNTs and the composites. The peaks at 882 and 962 cm⁻¹ are attributed to C–H wagging, while 1538 and 1454 cm⁻¹ represent the C=C stretching. C=N and C–N bonds of PPy are displayed via peaks at 1714 and 1298 cm⁻¹ respectively. The small peak at 3400 cm⁻¹ is related to the N–H stretching vibration¹³. The observed peaks confirm the formation of PPy via the polymerization process. Since the components of all the composites contain rGO and PPyNTs, their IR spectra are similar. The broad peak from 3600 to 3100 cm⁻¹ corresponds to the OH-stretching and OH-deformation vibration of the hydroxyl groups of graphene oxide, as well as the N–H stretching vibration from PPyNTs. The C=O stretching vibration of sp² carbon due to carboxylic group sites is represented at 1715 cm⁻¹. The peaks at 1096 and 1172 cm⁻¹

represent the C–O stretching vibrations, and the carbonyl groups remained during reduction⁶.

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was applied to characterize the chemical composition, oxidation state of the elements and functional groups of the composites (Figure 1 b, Table 1). According to the results obtained, composites exhibited similar peaks due to the presence of the same components. Signals from the C1s, N1s and O1s regions are displayed in the [Supplementary Figure 1](#). The C1s signal confirms the presence of rGO at 284.3 eV, corresponding to sp² carbon. The transition peaks at 291.1 eV display the plasmon loss features of delocalized conductive π -electrons labelled as π - π^* . The organic frameworks and oxidation on the surface could be attributed to the other C1s signals, such as sp³ (284.7 eV), C–O (286.1 eV), C=O (287.6 eV) and OC=O (288.8 eV). The N1s signal represents the PPyNTs components. The amount of nitrogen is relatively small, ranging from 0.8% to 1.7%, indicating that the rGO/PPyNT composites have mainly sp² carbon nanostructures and a small amount of nitrogen-containing PPyNTs nanostructures¹¹. The difference arises with Cu-MOF and Zn-MOF, where the amount of nitrogen is doubled after preparation. The MOF structure with Cu²⁺ helps and increase the incorporation of PPyNTs compared to Zn²⁺ MOF. The N1s peak shows signals typical for PPy as pyrrolic nitrogen (N1s signal at 399.8 eV) and PPy polaron signals (N1s signal at 401.3 eV for polaron and 402.5 eV for bipolaron), as well as some indication of pyridinic nitrogen at 398.0 eV (ref. 11).

BET assessment

The characterization of specific surface area and pore size distribution was done using the Brunauer–Emmett–Teller

(BET) method, leveraging nitrogen gas adsorption on the entire surface area of PPy-based composites at 77 K, corresponding to the boiling point of liquid nitrogen. We determined the specific surface area of rP20, rP40, rPCu, and rPZn to be 1.3, 4.22, 5.9, and 1.78 m^2/g respectively. This observation underscores the correlation between the increase in specific surface area, the augmented quantity of polypyrrole nanotubes and the incorporation of MOF structures containing Cu^{2+} and Zn^{2+} . Measurements of electrochemical activity are expected to reveal a similar trend due to the presence of the increasing of the specific areas of the samples. The adsorption isotherm illustrates absorbed gas quantity relative to pressure (Figure 2). Isotherms exhibit type III and IV patterns, indicating macro and mesoporous structures according to the IUPAC standards. However, rP20 and rP40 samples display a hybrid II/III isotherm, featuring a flatter region suggestive of monolayer formation and low material porosity at low pressure¹⁴. Mesoporous materials with 2–50 nm pore size and macroporous materials with pores exceeding 50 nm were identified. Pore size distribution curves revealed peaks concentrated in the mesoporous region, with rPCu exhibiting the main peak width in this range. The multi-peaks and varied distribution enhanced the intercalation/deintercalation processes, consistent with galvanostatic charge–discharge (GCD) results¹⁵, even at higher current densities. Moreover, rPCu displayed a prominent peak intensity (10–18 nm), indicating a direction path through the bulk material.

Morphology study

Figure 3 *a* illustrates the nanotube morphology of PPyNTs. TEM imaging reveals that these PPyNTs, guided by MO, feature internal cavities, primarily empty due to the MO

Figure 2. Nitrogen adsorption–desorption isotherms of the synthesized composites.

dissociation during cleaning (Figure 3 *b*). The average diameter of PPyNTs is approximately 0.06 μm . Figure 3 *c–f* depicts composites of rGO, PPyNTs and MOFs denoted as rP20, rP40, rPZn, and rPCu respectively. SEM images show rGO sheets formed via hydrothermal reduction, encapsulating PPyNTs to make the composites. The reaction at high temperatures results in rGO sheets with hydrophobic phrasal planes and hydrophilic edges^{2,11}. Before being oxidized, graphite has a layered structure that consists of rings of six carbon atoms arranged in widely spaced horizontal sheets, making the structure hydrophobic. Using Hummer’s method, GO sheets were exfoliated and different dispersion forms were produced, adding oxygen functional groups to their structure. After being reduced via the hydrothermal reaction, the rGO sheets were formed with some of the remaining oxygen functional groups. Those groups, together with PPyNTs inside the composites, can explain the hydrophilic edges of the composite. In contrast, the six-carbon ring structure of rGO also forms the hydrophobic phrasal planes of the composites.

The nano-size of PpyNTs makes them well dispersed inside the composite together with the MOFs. The dispersion of the components inside the rGO sheet matrix results in good porous structures, thus enhancing the electrolyte ion-adsorption ability during the electrochemical working process¹⁶. The interactions between PpyNTs, Zn/Cu-MOF and rGO also enhance the aero-stability of the composites. The similarity of the chemical bonds of the components in the composites can contribute to their interactions. Hence, it would increase the retention of the SC electrodes⁶.

Electrochemical characterizations

The electrochemical properties of the composites were studied in a three-electrode system to interpret the operating performance of the electrode materials. The electrochemical properties of the electrodes made using these composites are given in the [Supplementary Figure 2](#). We used the typical three-electrode system for the cyclic voltammetry (CV) test and GCD plot in a fixed potential window from -0.2 to 0.8 V using 1 M H_2SO_4 as the electrolyte. The shape of the CV curves changed gradually with increasing scan rates. This is due to the fact that the electrolyte ions do not have enough time to diffuse into the inner sites of the electrodes at high scan rates².

Figure 4 *a* shows the specific CV spectra of the composites at a scan rate of 10 mV/s. It is evident that as the percentage of PPyNTs in the composites increases from rP20 to rP40, the CV spectra of the electrodes exhibits higher current densities. The specific capacitance is directly proportional to the area under the CV curves, indicating that a higher amount of PPyNTs in the composite enhances the electrochemical performance of the device¹⁷. Additionally, the corresponding CV curves of the samples exhibit a cone-shaped form, as shown in Figure 4 *a*, attributed to

Figure 3. (a) SEM image of PPyNTs and (b) TEM image of PPyNTs. SEM images of composites (c) rP20, (d) rP40, (e) rPZn and (f) rPCu.

the irreversible degradation of the polymer redox capacity due to parasitic reactions¹⁸, which are electrochemical reactions starting to occur simultaneously and thus compete with the primary charge reactions as the electrode plates approach full charge.

A schematic view of the charge storage process occurring in the composites in the presence of H₂SO₄ as the electrolyte is given in [Supplementary Figure 3](#). It can be explained through the doping process, i.e. insertion and desertion of SO₄²⁻ ions in PPyNTs according to eq. (1):

where y is the doping degree, defined as the ratio between the number of charges in the polymer and the number of monomer units.

Since the MOFs of Zn²⁺ and Cu²⁺ were used as components of the composites, the samples showed redox peaks of faradaic reactions expressed as

where M denotes Zn or Cu from the MOFs and C is the carbon of the electrode¹⁹. The CV spectra of all samples from 10 to 100 mV/s are given in the [Supplementary Figure 2](#).

To further study the effect of PPyNTs on the working performance of the composites, GCD tests were conducted at different current densities from 0.5 to 5 A/g ([Supplementary Figure 3](#)). The specific capacitance value was calculated as

$$C_s = \frac{I \cdot \Delta t}{m \cdot \Delta V}, \quad (3)$$

where I denotes the applied current (A), Δt the time taken for discharge, m the mass of active electrode material and ΔV is the discharge potential⁶.

The GCD curves of the composites indicated that at low scanning rates, rPZn showed the highest discharging time, demonstrating a higher specific capacitance than the other samples. However, the accessibility of the electrolyte ions to the electrode surface decreased when the current density increased due to the shorter interaction times²⁰. The porous structure of the samples enhanced their ionic conductivity, while the composite components facilitated the ion transportability of the electrodes. This is evident in the SEM image, where the composites exhibit a porous surface that facilitates the penetration of electrolyte ions deep into the structure (Figure 3 e). During the charge/discharge process, the ions enter the composites through these porous surfaces. Hence, the ions can interact with the rGO, PPyNTs and MOFs inside the composites. An interaction can cause an ion transfer reaction, as explained in eq. (1). The SO₄²⁻ ions will react with PPyNTs to form [(PPy)^{2y+}(SO₄)_y²⁻], and release electrons via the insertion and desertion into the composites.

The specific capacitance data in rPZn demonstrated significant changes associated with current density (Figure 4 c). At 0.5 A/g, rPZn showed the highest specific capacitance of 270.1 F/g compared to 208.7 and 242.7 F/g for rP20 and rP40 respectively. However, when the scanning rates increased to 5 A/g, its specific capacitance dropped significantly to 149.5 F/g, smaller than 165 F/g for rPCu. However, both MOFs containing composites showed higher specific capacitance than the others. Figure 5 showed the large pore size of rPCu composites within the structures. Hence, it can explain the large specific area of rPCu leading to its high working performance. The bridges aid

Figure 4. Three-electrode system performance of (a) cyclic voltammetry at 10 mV/s, (b) charge-discharge plots at 0.5 A/g, (c) specific capacitance calculated from the galvanostatic charge-discharge curves, and (d) IR drop as a function of the current density of rP20, rP40, rPZn and rPCu.

Figure 5. Pore-size distribution of the synthesized composites based on PPyNTs with metal-organic framework.

charged ions in overcoming limitations related to intercalation and adsorption. Additionally, the porous structure enhances the likelihood of ion interaction, creating more favourable conditions for the reaction to occur²⁰.

Increasing PPyNT concentration to 40 vol.% displaces rGO in the composites, forming interconnected matrices.

However, higher concentration leads to PPyNT aggregation, reducing the rGO-formed porous bridges. It decreases electrolyte-ion interaction speed during GCD at higher sweep rates. The reduced porosity of rP40 limits charged-ion penetration compared to rP20, rPZn and rPCu. Through the reaction to form $[(\text{Ppy})^{2y+}(\text{SO}_4)_y^{2-}]$ and release of electrons, as explained in eq. (1), the increase in PPyNTs concentration would facilitate the possibility of interaction between the SO_4^{2-} ions and polymer chains. The higher concentration of PPyNTs inside rP40 also helps improve the pseudocapacitance of the composites, as can be seen from the higher CV curve of the composites (Figure 4 a). At a low sweep rate, the SO_4^{2-} ions penetrate deeply into the structure of rP40, enhancing its performance by interacting with the polymers. However, PPyNT aggregation impedes electrolyte-ion interaction. At high rates, electrolyte ions struggle to react with the polymer molecules inside the aggregates due to insufficient time²¹. Composites of rPZn and rPCu leverage the synergistic effect of PPyNTs and MOFs, enhancing both pseudocapacitance and electric double layer capacitance²². The diffusion of MOFs and PPyNTs improves electrolyte-ion contact during scanning²³, resulting in excellent pseudocapacitance in the composites.

Figure 4 d shows the IR drop variation at different current densities during the GCD test. The IR drop represents the potential difference across a conducting phase during

Figure 6. (a) Electrical impedance spectra and (b) cyclic capacity retention during 5000 cycles at 1 A/g of the composites.

current flow, reflecting changes in resistive impedance²⁴. GCD curves within the potential range -0.2 to 0.8 V show nearly triangular shape at low current density (0.5 A/g) for all samples. With increased current density, the IR drop changes intensify across all composites. Notably, rP20 exhibits the highest IR drop, indicating higher internal resistance than the others²⁵.

Electrochemical impedance and cyclic stability

A two-electrode symmetric SC was employed to study ion transport mechanisms and retention in the composites. Figure 6a shows semicircles in the high and mid-frequency regions of the Nyquist plots, reflecting charge transfer resistance (Rct)²⁶. Small Rct values indicate good capacitive behaviour, with rPCu exhibiting the lowest (1.4Ω), suggesting better retention²⁷. Conversely, rP20, rP40 and rPZn show higher Rct values, indicating potential retention drops²⁸. The slope of the oblique line in low-frequency regions represents the ion diffusion rate, with a rectilinear long imaginary axis indicating low diffusion resistance in composite electrode materials²⁷.

Figure 6b shows the cyclic stability of the composites at a current density of 1 A/g over 5000 cycles in a two-electrode symmetrical SC. Among the composites, rP40 exhibits lower charge-discharge stability due to the mechanical degradation of PPyNTs during doping/dedoping. Continuous interaction of PPyNTs with the electrolyte ions during SC operation alters the molecular structure, leading to the formation and release of $[(\text{PPy})_x^+(\text{SO}_4)_y^{2-}]$ species. These ongoing reactions degrade the polymer chains over repeated cycles, affecting the stability of the composites¹¹. The polymer degradation can explain the lower retention of rP40 since it has a higher concentration of PPyNTs than the other composites²⁹. With the addition of MOFs inside the composite, the aerospace structures was enhanced. It caused the stability for the structures during the long time testing, leading to high retention of the cells¹¹.

Conclusion

PPyNT/MOFs/rGO composites were synthesized using a one-step hydrothermal method and utilized as electrode materials in SCs. These materials exhibited promising performance in SCs with H_2SO_4 as the electrolyte. At low sweep rate, rPZn demonstrated the highest specific capacitance (270 F/g) due to the synergistic combination of EDLC and pseudocapacitance between rGO, PPyNTs and MOFs. However, at higher sweep rate, rPCu outperformed the others. Capacitance retention decreased with increasing PPyNT concentration, dropping to about 81% after 5000 cycles in rP40 due to PPyNT degradation during doping/dedoping. These findings highlight the potential of PPyNTs, MOFs and rGO-based materials as SC electrode components. Further research will optimize their composition to enhance performance.

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